

NOMINAL SUFFIXES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

The main goal of this research is to analyze formation of nouns in English language with the help of nominal suffixes.

The method used in this study is the contrastive descriptive method. The findings of the study reveal creation of new words using word formation rules in English language. The findings of this study could be used as effective teaching devices to teach and correct interference errors among learners.

INTRODUCTION

A characteristic of all human languages is the potential to create new words. Throughout the history of the English language new words have been incorporated into the language through borrowings as well as through the application of morphological and derivational rules to existing words and morphemes.

This article aims at studying the potential to create new words through word formation processes in both English language. Interest in word formation processes is probably as old as interest in language itself. Many of the questions that scholars are asking now were also being asked in the seventeenth, eighteenth and nineteenth centuries. [Bauer, 1983]

The two most common types of word formation in English language are derivation and compounding, both of which create new words from already existing morphemes. Derivation is the process by which a new word is created through the addition of affixes. On the other hand, compounding is a process involving the combination of two or more roots to give a new word. Other types of word formation are conversion, clipping, blends, and backformation.

BASIC MATERIAL

Derivation

It is the process of creating new words by adding prefixes and suffixes to the root of the existing word. It is one of the most important types of word formation in all languages. Derivation can be by adding a prefix to the root (rewrite) or a suffix (talker), as well as adding a prefix and a suffix at the same time (unhappiness) By means of derivation there are created new words by changing the grammatical category of the word to which it applies. There should be distinguished both types of affixes, the inflectional affixes and the derivational affixes. The inflectional affixes, which are only eight of them, merely modify a word (table- tables, bird- bird's, stay- stays- stayed -staying), whereas derivational affixes create a new

word of another grammatical category for example.: happy –happiness; taste –tasty; real – realize.

Suffixes

Noun formation can be found in the works of many researchers such as Comrie and Thomson (1985), using different languages to illustrate manner, locative, objective and reason nominalization, concluded that the derived nouns from lexical verbs and adjectives may be classified into two broad groups: name of activity or state designated by the verb or adjective. These are action/state nouns which are action nouns created from action verbs and state nouns created from stative verbs and adjectives.

Arnoff [1976:21] claims that only nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs can be the product of word formation, and that only these form classes can be used bases in the formation of derivations. Bauer, however [1973:225] argues that the first part of this claim may be true, but there is plenty of evidence that minor form classes can be used as bases in established forms like downer, inness, whyness, etc.

On his book "Word-formation in English" [2003], Plag studies different types of suffixes: verbal suffixes, nominal suffixes, adjectival suffixes, adverbial suffixes.

Nominal suffixes

According to Plag [2003], nominal suffixes are often employed to derive abstract nouns from verbs, adjectives and nouns. Such abstract nouns can denote actions, results of actions, or other related concepts, but also properties, qualities and the like. One way of classifying noun-forming suffixes in English can be either with reference to the resulted word-class after a suffix has been added to a base, or with reference to the grammatical class of the base to which they are added. For instance, the suffix **-ee** at the end of a word like absentee is a noun suffix because the addition of this suffix results in the formation of a noun. Meanwhile, this suffix, in the same example, has a de-adjectival function in the sense that it is added to the adjective (absent).

In view of these principles of classification, suffixes in English can be discussed in terms of the following types and subtypes:

-ant (as well as -ent) = who / that carries out, agentive and instrumental: informant, claimant, solvent, inhabitant, disinfectant, servant.

-er = also **-or** in words of latin origin: server, dreamer, cleaner, recorder.

-ing = agentive: the working (a definite article is mandatory); added to: verbs; = activity: swimming, gardening, manufacturing; added to: verbs; = result: building, clothing, painting.

-ee = passive, affected by: employee, interviewee, trustee, evacuee; added to: verbs. The resulting noun must denote a person.

-ed = passive, affected by: the unemployed.

-eer = denoting the person carrying out a certain action: auctioneer, sloganeer, volunteer.

-ery = also **-ry** = brewery, bakery.

-ist: communist, fascist, royalist; converted from: abstract nouns ending -ism or added to certain adjectives (royal); Also it has the meaning (a person practising science or art, trade or profession: archaeologist, violinist, tobacconist, dentist.

CONCLUSION

This study aimed to give an overview of the main types of the word formation types in English language consulting various sources of information, mostly grammars and articles by foreign

linguists. The focus of this work was the study of the vocabulary enrichment by means of word formation processes, the ones which result as the most productive in creating new words.

In the derivational process, in English language, nominal suffixes are used to create new words.

To conclude, English language has the potential to create new words by means of the word formation process, by which a wide range of new words are created in English .

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